

**BRIGHT
SPACE**

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Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

This is the 1st newsletter of the BrightSpace project WHERE YOU CAN:

- Find out what BrightSpace is all about
- Read about the latest developments of the project
- Know more about networking with other EU projects
- Get information on upcoming events

What is BrightSpace ?

BrightSpace is an EC funded 5-year Horizon Europe research and innovation action aiming to design effective and sustainable strategies to navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space.

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Meet the BrightSpace project team

The consortium of BrightSpace consists of 14 partners from 9 countries in Europe (AT, CZ, FR, DE, HU, IT, NL, ES, UK) and the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission.

The consortium includes partners from the private and public sector representing:

- (a) academia and higher education (CZU, UBO, UCSC, UOXF, WU);
- (b) SME dealing with research consultancy, data collection, development (EuroCARE). Another SME has also a strong track record in the field of communication, stakeholder engagement and exploitation (PLAB);
- (c) public government bodies dealing with agricultural and environmental research and data collection, and building agricultural models at different scales (WR, CITA, IIASA, Thünen, INRAE, PBL, TC CAS).

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Project structure

The BrightSpace project is managed through 11 work packages (WP), each of which oversees and/or are responsible for various parts of the five-year project.

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Latest news from BrightSpace

BrightSpace 1st General Assembly Meeting

14 partners from 9 countries in Europe (AT, CZ, FR, DE, HU, IT, NL, ES, UK) and the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission came together in The Hague on 30 November 2022 to mark the start of the five-year research project BrightSpace.

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Media Coverage: Article In Heraldo De Aragón

Read the article online about BrightSpace titled "Modelos de simulación para equilibrar economía y medio ambiente en el sector agroalimentario" (Simulation models to balance economy and environment in the agri-food sector).

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2nd WP1 Meeting

The main objective of WP1 is to define a conceptual framework for the identification of drivers and indicators in order to 1) obtain an enhanced concept for SJOS 2) identify operational and valid SJOS indicators...

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Creating Synergies: BrightSpace Presented In Prague Workshop

The Technology Centre Prague in cooperation with CAAEES and SEEPIA organized a hybrid workshop on modelling of agriculture and policy impacts on 8 March 2023.

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Networking and Cooperation with Horizon Europe Projects

BrightSpace Collaborates With Fellow Project LAMASUS

Cooperation activities are envisaged with the LAMASUS project funded under the “HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-13 – Modelling land use and land management in the context of climate change” topic.

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Networking And Cooperation With Horizon Europe Projects: GenBEcon And RATION

BrightSpace established cooperation in January 2023 with the two Horizon Europe research projects. Joint activities involve regular monthly meetings of project teams to share information on research progress and outputs...

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Upcoming project events

Pre-Congress Workshop: Towards New Baseline Scenarios In Ex Ante Modelling Of Land-Use And -Management

Join us for the pre-congress session of the LAMASUS and Brightspace Horizon Europe Projects from 09:00 AM to 1:00 PM on 29th August 2023 in the XVII EAAE Congress venue Couvent des Jacobins in Rennes, France.

[Read more »](#)

Pre-Congress Workshop: Challenges For Implementing The EU Farm-To-Fork Strategy – Pests, Plants, And Profits

Join us for the pre-congress workshop where we present and discuss the Inter-model Cooperation between the Brightspace, GeneBEcon, and RATION Projects from 09:00 AM to 12:00 PM on 29 August 2023 in the XVII EAAE Congress venue Couvent des Jacobins in Rennes, France.

[Read more »](#)

Watch our videos

Follow us on Youtube: <https://www.youtube.com/@brightspace-horizon-eu-project>

Upcoming events

AIEAA Conference 2023

Food Security and Food Systems in a Risky World

22-23 June 2023

UNIVERSITY OF MILANO, ITALY

AIEAA Conference, 22-23 June 2023, IT

The Conference aims to discuss how shocks – such as extreme weather events, health-related shocks or anthropogenic conflicts – are affecting food systems and explore how food systems can be reformed to be better prepared to absorb, adapt and transform in the face of shocks as well as to slow onset disruptions.

[Read more »](#)

EAAE congress 2023

Food systems in a changing world:
Connecting Science and Society

29 August – 1 September

RENNES, FRANCE

XVII EAAE Congress, 29 August – 1 September 2023, FR

The XVII Congress of the European Association of Agricultural Economists (EAAE) “Agri-food systems in a changing world: Connecting science and society” will be held in Rennes, France from August 29 to September 1, 2023.

[Read more »](#)

Visit our website for more upcoming events: <https://brightspace-project.eu/>

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More information will be sent in our next BrightSpace newsletter scheduled for autumn 2023.

Thank you for signing up to the [BrightSpace newsletters](#).

Further information can be found on the BrightSpace project homepage:

<https://brightspace-project.eu/>

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